

Trace Element Status of Soils of the Union Territory of Delhi

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The micronutrient status of the intensive cropping areas of the Union Territory of Delhi has been examined. The total contents of copper, zinc, iron, manganese and molybdenum as well as the available manganese, boron and zinc contents of the soils were fairly satisfactory for sustaining high crop production. The available copper and iron were found satisfactory only in paddy growing areas while these were either marginal or deficient in most of the bajra/maize growing soils. Available boron content in some soils was in the toxic range.

Organic matter showed significant positive relationship with available boron, copper and zinc. Available boron and manganese were significantly affected by CaCO_3 . Available manganese also showed significant relationship with soil pH. Available iron showed significant positive relationship with clay content.

TRACE element deficiency in cereal crops have been reported from different States in our country. As the use of high yielding varieties and high analysis fertilizers is becoming popular in an intensive cropping system, continual depletion of micronutrients from the surface soil may lead to micronutrient deficiency in soils which receive no micronutrient fertilizer and which have low reserve of micronutrients. A survey has been made to study the micronutrient status of the soils of the intensive cropping areas of the Union Territory of Delhi.

Experimental

Soil samples from 0-20 cm depth were collected from the intensive cropping areas of the Union Territory after the harvest of paddy and bajra/or maize crops. The cropping sequence is usually either bajra/maize-wheat or paddy-wheat. 18 soil samples were collected from paddy growing areas and 17 soil samples were collected from bajra/maize growing areas. The soil samples were prepared by procedure described by Jackson¹ for total and available micronutrient analysis.

Soil pH, organic C, CaCO_3 content, soil texture were determined by the conventional methods as described by Jackson¹. Total Zn, Cu, Fe and Mn in soil were estimated in the triacid extract of the HF-HClO₄ digested soil (Jackson¹). Total Mo has been estimated by the procedure of Reisenauer² in the HClO₄ extract of soil.

The available Zn was determined³ in 0.1N HCl and in 0.01% dithizone+1N neutral NH₄OAc extracts⁴. The available Cu was determined⁵ in 0.1N HCl and 1N NH₄OAc pH 4.8 extracts⁶. The available Fe was determined in 1N NH₄OAc pH 4.8 extract⁷. The available Mn was determined⁸ in 3N NH₄H₂PO₄ and 1N neutral NH₄OAc extracts⁹. The available B was determined in hot water extract¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

The soils under investigation had pH range 7.1 to 8.8, CaCO_3 1.0 to 3.5%, organic matter 0.46 to 2.34%, clay 5.0 to 35.0% and texture varying from clay loam to sand.

The total micronutrient status of the soils has been presented in Table 1. It is evident from table that the total copper content ranged from 20 to 48 ppm and 14 to 84 ppm having average of 32.9 and 30.6 ppm in paddy and bajra/maize soils, respectively. The total iron content in bajra/maize soils ranged from 0.9 to 2.2% with an average of 1.4%, while in paddy soils it ranged from 1.2 to 2.5% with an average of 1.8%. The total manganese content of paddy soils varied from 272 to 709 ppm having an average of 415 ppm. In bajra/maize soils, it ranged from 182 to 491 ppm having an average of 356 ppm. The total zinc content varied from 37 to 97 ppm and 29 to 126 ppm having average of 63 and 89 ppm in paddy and bajra/maize soils, respectively. The total molybdenum content of paddy soils ranged from 1.7 to 3.4 ppm with an average of 2.5 ppm and 1.2 to 2.9 ppm with an average of 2.0 ppm in bajra/maize soils.

The total content of trace elements in soils showed considerable variation suggesting the importance of parent material and soil management practices in building up the total reserve of the trace elements in soil. Dakshinamurti *et al.*¹¹ reported that the total Cu and Zn contents of virgin Delhi soils lie in the range of 8.1 to 21.7 ppm and 4.0 to 41.4 ppm, respectively. The results of the present investigation indicate a much higher range of Cu and Zn in cultivated soils of Delhi. Very high values of Cu and Zn were found in soils where sewage water is used (soil nos. 3, 14, 19, 31, & 32) for irrigating the land. The total Mo content of the cultivated soils, however, was found to lie within the range given by Dakshinamurti *et al.*¹¹ for virgin Delhi soils. The total Mn content of Delhi soils lies in the range of 363 to 621

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TABLE 1. TOTAL MICRONUTRIENT STATUS OF DELHI SOILS

Soil No.	Copper (ppm)	Iron (per cent)	Manganese (ppm)	Zinc (ppm)	Molybdenum (ppm)
1	28	1.7	272	46	1.7
2	26	1.8	345	43	2.3
3	46	1.5	382	91	3.4
4	34	1.7	436	51	2.9
5	40	1.8	454	49	3.4
6	32	1.9	382	46	2.9
7	20	1.7	418	37	1.7
8	32	1.2	391	43	1.7
9	30	1.8	454	51	2.3
10	32	2.1	709	74	3.4
11	32	1.8	327	66	2.3
12	28	2.1	464	71	2.0
13	28	1.9	400	66	3.4
14	40	1.5	418	89	2.0
15	24	1.4	382	49	2.3
16	34	2.5	400	97	3.4
17	38	1.6	345	94	2.0
18	48	2.5	491	74	2.6
19	48	1.5	436	94	2.3
20	32	1.1	327	91	2.9
21	22	1.4	418	43	2.0
22	24	1.5	327	34	1.7
23	22	1.2	418	40	1.7
24	14	1.3	182	29	1.2
25	32	2.2	391	51	2.9
26	16	1.2	327	43	1.7
27	14	0.9	207	31	2.3
28	16	0.9	254	46	2.6
29	22	1.4	427	43	1.7
30	24	1.9	491	46	2.3
31	84	1.5	454	120	2.3
32	76	1.4	400	126	2.0
33	20	0.9	382	57	1.4
34	32	1.6	227	42	1.7
35	22	1.7	382	60	1.7

N.B. Soil Nos. 1 to 18 having paddy-wheat, 19 to 30 bajra-wheat and 31 to 35 having maize-wheat rotations.

ppm according to Biswas¹² which is in good agreement with the present findings.

The available micronutrient status of the soils with respect to different extractants has been presented in Table 2. It is evident from table that available boron ranged from 0.9 to 15.2 ppm with an average of 3.8 ppm and 0.9 to 4.8 ppm with an average of 2.8 ppm in paddy and bajra/maize soils, respectively. Since 0.5 ppm is the sufficiency limit for available boron in soil (Chapman and Pratt¹³), all the soils under study have adequate level of available boron. Some soils have got higher than 3.25 ppm of available boron, which according to Richards¹⁴ are likely to be toxic for normal crop production. Organic matter and CaCO₃ contents of soil showed significant positive correlation with available boron ($r = 0.45$ and 0.48 , respectively) in soils which is in accordance with the findings of Singh and Singhal¹⁵.

Available copper in 0.1N HCl extract ranged from 1.7 ppm to 20 ppm having an average of 4.8 ppm, in 1N NH₄OAc pH 4.8 extract ranged from 0.08 ppm to 2.00 ppm having an average of 0.43 ppm in paddy

soils. In bajra/maize soils it ranged from 0.90 to 37.0 ppm with an average of 6.3 ppm in 0.1N HCl and 0.06 to 3.12 ppm with an average of 0.56 ppm in 1N NH₄OAc extract.

According to the sufficiency limit of 2 ppm in 0.1N HCl soluble Cu as given by Chapman and Pratt¹³, all the soils except 8, 15, 24, 28, 33 and 34 are adequately supplied with available Cu. The available Cu content in NH₄OAc pH 4.8 extract also showed adequate amount in most of the soils except 8, 9, 10, 15 and 16 according to the critical limit of 0.2 ppm as given by Fiskell⁹. Organic matter

TABLE 2. AVAILABLE MICRONUTRIENT STATUS OF DELHI SOILS (PPM)

Soil No.	Copper		Iron	Manganese		Zinc		Boron
	1§	2		4	5	6	7	
1	2.6	0.28	4.3	36.4	9.4	2.6	1.2	2.2
2	4.2	0.24	9.5	36.4	21.1	3.4	1.4	3.3
3	20.0	2.00	4.6	47.3	22.2	20.0	7.7	2.8
4	3.2	0.38	5.5	34.5	21.9	4.6	1.3	1.6
5	2.8	0.22	6.5	40.0	16.1	2.0	0.6	1.4
6	3.2	0.44	8.3	48.2	19.6	3.4	1.0	2.9
7	3.0	0.64	8.3	80.0	36.1	2.7	0.6	1.2
8	1.7	0.08	0.5	47.3	14.9	3.4	0.6	1.1
9	2.0	0.10	1.5	43.6	12.3	4.3	1.6	1.5
10	2.4	0.16	2.5	32.7	5.1	5.0	1.3	0.9
11	2.9	0.28	2.5	40.0	21.4	2.5	1.3	5.9
12	3.0	0.24	1.5	47.2	23.1	2.9	1.0	3.8
13	2.3	0.22	4.2	43.6	17.8	1.7	1.2	10.4
14	15.0	1.24	8.9	25.5	6.2	20.7	7.2	2.9
15	1.8	0.16	1.2	40.0	12.3	2.5	1.2	15.2
16	2.2	0.10	0.3	67.3	16.1	4.6	2.2	2.4
17	8.0	0.60	4.3	43.6	10.1	8.9	2.7	5.4
18	5.8	0.45	23.4	36.4	9.8	5.0	2.2	3.1
19	18.5	1.40	3.7	43.6	5.8	23.5	7.4	4.6
20	6.1	0.46	1.4	36.4	23.6	14.6	4.6	1.4
21	2.6	0.22	0.8	40.0	13.5	11.4	3.4	1.3
22	2.0	0.17	2.5	32.7	6.8	3.2	1.7	3.2
23	2.4	0.10	2.0	29.1	14.9	1.8	1.3	2.7
24	0.9	0.06	0.9	20.0	2.3	1.0	1.0	0.9
25	1.5	0.10	0.6	49.1	16.1	1.4	1.0	2.8
26	2.8	0.12	1.2	32.7	5.1	4.3	1.9	4.8
27	2.4	0.12	0.9	32.7	6.9	3.2	1.6	3.8
28	1.9	0.08	1.1	23.4	14.1	2.9	1.9	3.4
29	2.2	0.18	2.8	50.9	6.1	2.9	1.6	2.4
30	2.0	0.14	0.9	30.9	12.0	3.2	1.4	2.1
31	18.5	3.12	2.6	45.5	5.8	32.0	18.6	3.3
32	37.0	3.10	1.4	43.6	2.9	32.2	18.8	4.0
33	1.6	0.08	1.8	45.5	10.5	2.2	1.2	2.0
34	1.8	0.06	0.5	36.4	10.9	2.9	1.3	2.0
35	2.4	0.06	19.7	40.0	14.9	2.7	0.6	2.2

§ 1. 0.1N HCl, 2. 1N NH₄OAc, pH 4.8, 3. 1N NH₄OAc pH 4.8, 4. 3N NH₄H₂PO₄, 5. 1N NH₄OAc pH 7.0, 6. 0.1N HCl, 7. 0.01% dithizone+1N NH₄OAc, 8. Hot water extract.

showed significant positive relationship ($r = 0.33$ and 0.37) with available Cu which is in agreement with the observations of Grewal *et al.*¹⁶. Soil pH, CaCO₃ and clay contents of soil did not show any significant relationship with available Cu.

Available iron in 1*N* NH₄OAc pH 4.8 extract ranged from 0.3 to 23.4 ppm with an average of 5.4 ppm in paddy soils and 0.5 to 19.7 ppm with an average of 2.6 ppm in bajra/maize soils. The available iron in paddy soils was adequate leaving aside some exceptions e.g., soils nos. 8, 9, 12, 15 and 16 where the available iron content was less than the critical limit of 2 ppm (Olson and Carlson⁷). In bajra/maize soils, 11 out of 17 soils were inadequately supplied with available iron indicating the possibility of occurring iron deficiency in plants. Clay content of soil showed significant positive relationship ($r = 0.47$) with available iron. Other soil characters did not show any significant bearing on the available iron.

Available manganese in 3*N* NH₄H₂PO₄ extract ranged from 25.5 to 80.0 ppm in paddy soils and 20.0 to 50.9 ppm in bajra/maize soils with an average of 37.2 ppm. The exchangeable manganese in paddy soils ranged from 5.1 to 36.1 ppm with an average of 10.1 ppm in bajra/maize soils. Chapman and Pratt¹³ suggested 20 ppm manganese as adequate level in 3*N* NH₄H₂PO₄ extract and according to this limit all the soils are adequately supplied with available manganese. The critical limit for exchangeable manganese is 3 ppm (Sherman *et al.*⁹). All the soils under study showed higher than this level. CaCO₃ and pH showed significant relationship with available manganese ($r = 0.33$ and -0.77 , respectively), whereas exchangeable manganese did not show any significant relationship with the soil characters studied.

Available zinc in 0.1*N* HCl extract ranged from 1.7 to 20.7 ppm with an average of 5.5 ppm in paddy soils and 1.0 to 32.2 ppm with an average of 8.0 ppm in bajra/maize soils. Available zinc in NH₄OAc + dithizone extract 0.6 to 7.7 ppm with an average of 2 ppm in paddy soils and 0.6 to 18.8 ppm having an average of 4.1 ppm in bajra/maize soils.

Available zinc in 0.1*N* HCl extract showed satisfactory level in all the soils according to the critical

limit of 1 ppm as suggested by Sharma and Motiramani¹⁷. Dithizone + NH₄OAc extractable zinc also showed sufficiency levels as all the soils showed values higher than 0.5 ppm which is the critical level given by Brown *et al.*¹⁸. Organic matter showed significant positive correlation ($r = 0.34$) with 0.1*N* HCl zinc which is in agreement with the findings of Sharma and Motiramani¹⁷. Other soil characters did not show any significant relationship with available zinc in soil.

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